
ASSESSMENT OF GROUNDWATER POTENTIAL OF LAFIA, MIDDLE BENUE TROUGH USING VERTICAL ELECTRICAL SOUNDING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Electrical resistivity method was employed to investigate the groundwater potential of Lafia, Nasarawa State. The study was carried out using ABEM SAS Terrameter, schlumberger electrode configuration was used to acquire twenty seven (27) vertical electrical sounding (VES) across the study area. The VES obtain were interpreted by using IPI2Win computer software which reveal three to six geo-electric layer. The results of the interpreted VES results show that the resistivity of the aquifer layers varies from 129ohm to 902ohm with average of 465. The thickness varies from 10.06m to 32.50m with an average of 21m. While the depth to the aquifer layers varies from 12m to 60m with an average of 40m. The vertical electrical sounding curve types identified in the study area includes K, A, Q and H type. About 21.73% of the sounding curves belong to the KH-type whereas the remaining 48.15% belong to other curve types as indicated within the study area. Therefore, KH is the most dominant sounding curve type in the study area.

KEYWORDS; Groundwater, vertical electrical sounding (VES), Schlumberger array, resistivity, aquifer.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

Groundwater has always been considered to be a readily available source of water for domestic, agricultural and industrial use. In many parts of the world groundwater extracted for a variety of purposes has made a major contribution to the improvement of the social and economic circumstances of humans (Biswas, 1998). It can also be seen that fresh water is also found in lakes, streams, springs but rain water constitute very small percentage of the total natural water supply. The water located beneath the ground surface in the saturated zone, is usually abstracted through a well, dug or drilled. The depth of the well and thus the cost of constructing it, depend on the distance from the surface to the groundwater aquifer, ranging from a few meters to several hundred (Clark, 1996). The potential yield depends on the size of the aquifer, and to be sustainable, withdrawal must not exceed the natural rate of recharge (Clark, 2004). The cost of abstracting groundwater, including the cost of pumping, tends to be higher than that of surface waters (Ganz, 2003). Being located beneath the ground, water quality and temperature is relatively constant over time, and turbidity, microbiological contamination and content of organic matter is usually lower than in surface water. The content of minerals is generally higher in groundwater, as these substances are dissolved from the rocks and soils in which the water resides (Akankpo and Igboekwe, 2011; Nwankwo and Igboekwe, 2011).

Groundwater is the safest and most reliable water source, used for domestic, irrigation, industrial, and municipality purposes. Ground water development for water supply purposes is preferable to low discharge springs and dug wells because they are found to be adequate in their yield and resistant to drought while other sources might be completely dried out and never easily recovered after the prolonged drought time. The occurrence, origin, movement and chemical constituents of groundwater are dependent on geology/lithology, geomorphology/landforms, drainage density, rainfall, geological structures/lineaments, slope, land use/land cover and soil of groundwater regime. It is common to have problem in exploitation of groundwater resource in that unsuccessful rate of well production encountered is alarming and have cost huge waste of resources. Improper evaluation of groundwater and site selections is mostly expected to pose problems (Shiferaw and Abebe, 2004). Since the groundwater occurs not in our sight but deep in the subsurface, there is no direct method to facilitate observation of water below the surface. Its presence or absence can only be inferred indirectly by studying the groundwater occurrence and distribution controlling parameters (MacDonald, et al., 2001).

Groundwater can be in sedimentary terrain where it is less difficult to exploit except for its chemical composition; it can also be in the Basement Complex terrain where it can be a bit difficult to locate especially in areas underlain by crystalline unfractured or unweathered rocks (Ahilan et al., 2010).

The research for groundwater today has become essential, due to its relative low cost and its chance of obtaining quality water from the bedrock. In hard rock areas, the geological structure normally encountered is characterized by the existence of a hard rock basement overlain by a weathered overburden of variable thickness.

Hydrogeologically, the weathered material, which constitutes the overburden, has high porosity and contains a significant amount of water, and, at the same time, it presents low permeability due to its relatively high clay content. The bedrock, on the other hand, is fresh but frequently fractured, presenting high permeability, but as fractures do not constitute a

significant volume of the rock, fractured basement has a low porosity. For this reason, a good borehole providing long term high yields, is one which penetrates a large thickness of weathered overburden, which acts as a reservoir, and one which additionally intersects fractures in the underlying bedrock, where the fractures provide the rapid transport mechanism (Rai et al., 2005).

Several methods use for groundwater exploration include electrical resistivity, gravity, seismic, magnetic, remote sensing, electromagnetic, among others, out of which the resistivity method is most effective for locating productive well and the Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) technique can provide information on the vertical variation in the resistivity of the ground with depth (Rhett, 2001). Evidence has shown that geophysical methods are the most reliable and the most accurate means of all surveying method of subsurface structural investigations and rock variation.

1.2 Location, Extent, Accessibility and Sample locations

The Study Area is part of Lafia Sheet 231NW, published by the office of the Surveyor General of the Federation, Abuja Nigeria, 2008. The study area falls within Nasarawa state and lies between latitude $08^{\circ}15'00''\text{N}$ $8^{\circ}30'20''\text{N}$ and longitudes $08030'00''\text{E}$ - $08045'50''\text{E}$. It covers an area extent of $35.\text{km}^2$ In terms of accessibility; the area is accessible through Lafia-Obi road, Lafia-Makurdi road and Lafia-Jos road. The area is also accessible through rural road and foot path linking the various areas. The VES points are been carried out the accessible locations within the study area.

Fig. 1a. Location and accessibility map of the study area.

Fig. 1b VES point locations within the study area.

2.0 Geology of the Study Area

The Geology of Lafia is dominated by the Benue Trough, a sedimentary basin that contains complex formations, which are the Lafia formation and Awgu formation. Lafia formation made up of sandstone, siltstones and bands of mudstone while the Awgu formation is made up of shale with little sandstone.

Fig. 2 Geological Map of the Study Area

2.0 Climate and Vegetation

The study area is under the influence of two major weather conditions, namely: the rainy season which starts in April and ends in October with its peak in July/august; and the dry season begins in October and ends in March. The annual rainfall recorded ranges between 1250mm to 1500mm while the annual temperature is 90-95°F or 32-36°C, with February to April being the hottest period of the year (Barber and Depreez, 1965). By February and March, the river channels are almost totally dry, providing easy access to outcrops exposed by rivers. The study area lies within the Guinea savannah belt of Nigeria characterized by preponderance of tall grasses dotted by few giant trees, except for the river channels which support rain forest vegetation characterized by deciduous trees. Generally, the vegetation is sparsely distributed on a flat land and denser along the stream channel.

3.0 Material and method

3.1 Materials

- ABEM Terrameter
- Four stainless steel current and potential electrodes
- Four single core cable reels for current and potential electrodes
- Hammers for coupling electrodes into the ground
- Measuring tapes for marking out electrode spacing
- The Golden SURFER 20 was used to produce the aquifer thickness, hydraulic conductivity map, aquifer transmissivity and the vulnerability map of the study area.

3.2 Methods

Resistivity measurements were made with a Terrameter SAS 300B system. An accurate and dependable method of interpretation of VES data was employed in this study. This involves

the use of computer method in conjunction with the visual inspection, which involves the identification of the VES curves based on the shape of the various curves produced from the field data and hence infers the relative magnitudes of the different geoelectric layers. Field data were plotted on bi-logarithmic coordinate as sounding curves, representing the variations of the apparent resistivity as function of half current electrode spacing; a smooth curve can be drawn through the points to generate field curves.

3.2.1 Field Procedures

- **Site selection:** A suitable location for the survey was selected away from power lines and other sources of electrical noise
- **Equipment setup:** Set up the VES equipment including ABEM terrameter SAS 300B system, electrodes (current and potential), cables.
- **Electrode deployment:** Deploy the current electrode (C1 and C2) at a fixed distance. Ensure electrode are in contact with the ground.
- **Data acquisition:** Inject current into the ground through C1 and C2, Measure the potential differences between P1 and P2. Record the resistivity values of each electrode spacing.
- **Data analysis:** Use software e.g IPI2Win to analyse data generate a resistivity depth profile
- **Interpretation:** Identify subsurface layers and their resistivity values correlate with geological or hydrogeological features.

Fig. 3 Schlumberger Configuration

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The result of the twenty-seven VES carried out across the study area revealed the existence of three to six layers (**Fig.4.1**) within the area. The distribution of resistivity of different subsurface layers in a three layered earthmodel can be classified based on curve shapes into H-type ($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3$), K-type ($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3$), A-type ($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3$) and Q-type ($\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3$). Different curve types were identified in the study area based on the numbers of layers- A, KH, AQ, KHK, HA, H, QH, HK, HK curvestypes.

Table 1: Characteristics Curve type in the study area with their frequency and percentage

S/NO	Curve type	Curve characteristics	Curve frequency	% curve type
1.	H	P1>p2<p3	4	17.39
2.	KH	P1<p2>p3<p4	5	21.73
4.	KHK	P1>p2<p3>p4<p5	2	8.69
5.	HK	P1>p2<p3>p4	3	13.04
6.	QH	P1>p2>p3<p4	1	4.34
7.	HA	P1>p2<p3<p4	3	13.04
8.	A	P1<p2<p3	2	8.69
10.	K	P1<p2>p3	1	4.34

4.1.1 Aquifer Parameters

Table 2 represents the hydraulic parameters of the aquifers in Lafia and are important properties for both groundwater and contaminated land assessments and for safe construction of engineering infrastructure.

Table 2: Aquifer parameters estimated from VES data

VES NO	Aquifer Thickness b(m)	Aquifer Resistivity ρ (ohm-m)	Transverse Resistance (ohm-m ²)	Longitudinal Conductance (ohm ⁻¹)	Hydraulic conductivity Kc (cm/s)	Transmissivity Tc (cm ² /s)
1	21.00	49.40	1037.4	0.42510	0.02024291	0.4251009
2	1.09	43.70	47.63	0.0249479	0.00228832	0.00249426
3	10.06	29.00	307.4	0.36557724	0.0344827	0.36551662
4	22.90	325	7377.5	0.06984615	0.00307692	0.08556084
5	37.10	156	5787.6	0.23782051	0.00641025	0.23782027
6	18.08	288	5207.04	0.06277777	0.00347222	0.06277737
7	10.95	228	2452.8	0.04802631	0.00438596	0.04780696
8	25.10	129	3237.9	0.1945736	0.00775193	0.19457344
9	16.04	287	4603.48	0.05588850	0.00348432	0.05588849
10	15.10	902	13620.2	0.01674057	0.00110865	0.01674056
11	8.84	864	763.77	0.102314814	0.01157407	0.10231477
12	15.90	166	13069.8	0.019343065	0.00121654	0.01934298
13	6.38	146	931.48	0.038433734	0.00684931	0.04369859
14	6.75	410	31037	0.184634146	0.00243902	0.01646338
15	12.10	660	7986	0.018333333	0.00151515	0.01833333
16	32.50	172	5590	0.18895348	0.005813953	0.18895347
17	10.90	465	5068.5	0.023440860	0.002150537	0.02344085
18	28.80	346	9964	0.08323699	0.002890173	0.083236982
19	20.81	416	8656.9	0.05002403	0.00240384	0.050023910
20	7.44	89.50	665.88	0.083128491	0.01173184	0.087284889
21	20.04	192	3847.68	0.104375	0.0052083	0.10437433
22	19.75	246	4814.22	0.079552849	0.00406504	0.07955283
23	22.20	343	7614.6	0.06472303	0.00291545	0.06472301
24	32.80	168	5510.4	0.19523809	0.00595238	0.195238064
25	6.37	1149	7319.13	0.00554395	0.00087032	0.005543893
26	19.88	322	1249.36	0.01204968	0.003105590	0.061739129
27	23.55	458	1625.90	0.00775109	0.00218340	0.05141907

4.1.2 Aquifer Resistivity

Fig 4. represents the apparent-resistivity map of Lafia showing the resistivity distribution of the aquifer layers and had been proven useful in mapping promising areas for groundwater abstraction. The south eastern, north western and western area of the map showed lower resistivity while the southern part indicated high value of resistivity. The legend of the map can be used as a guide in locating the areas with various resistivity value.

Figure 4.: Resistivity Map of the Study Area

4.1.3 Aquifer Thickness

Fig 5. represents the thickness map of the aquifers in Lafia, it showed that the thickness of the aquifer computed from the resistivity soundings interpretation ranges from 1.09 to 37.10 meters. Maximum aquifer thickness values were observed in VES 5, 16, 24, 18, 23, 19, 21 and 4 with values ranging above 20 meters. The thickness tends to spread throughout the map; this indicates that the aquifer of the area is thick and prolific which can be tapped by many productive boreholes and wells. The higher thickness is located in the northwest, part of north central and southwest side of the map.

Fig 5. Aquifer Thickness Map of the Study Area

4.1.4 Hydraulic conductivity

Fig 6. shows the hydraulic conductivity map of the study area. The calculated hydraulic conductivity values estimated from the VES results ranges from 0.00060716 to 0.02024291 cm/s. The maximum hydraulic conductivity is observed at the Northwest part of the study area while the hydraulic conductivity value tends to decrease towards the north Eastern and also part of the southern part of the map.

Fig 6. Hydraulic Conductivity Map of the Study Area

4.1.5 Transmissivity

Fig 7. represents the transmissivity map of Lafia. Transmissivity is a measure of how much water can be transmitted horizontally. Transmissivity values of the study area ranges from 2.5754 to 38.6325cm²/s as shown in Table 6, thus, suggesting a reasonable quality of reservoir. The fundamental knowledge of transmissivity is a fundamental source of information for establishing a hydrogeological model. From the Map the blue regions tends to have lower transmissivity value while the green, yellow and red regions tends to have a higher transmissivity value which shows a prolific zone for groundwater development.

Fig. 7. Transmissivity Map of the Study Area

4.2 Discussion

The map (Fig. 8) presents local groundwater prospects of the study area which is zoned into high, medium and low groundwater potentials which is a function of the properties of the aquifer probed.

High groundwater zone are zones that have high level of transmissivity which is also a function of high hydraulic conductivity, large aquifer thickness and low resistivity. Medium groundwater zone are zones that have medium level of transmissivity while low groundwater zone are zones with low level of transmissivity.

Areas with blue color on the map constitute the low groundwater potential zone while areas with green to yellow color constitute the medium groundwater potential zone. Red colour

represents the high groundwater potential zone. Region of high groundwater potential generally lies in the Western part of the map.

Fig 8. Groundwater Potential Map of the Study Area

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

• Conclusion

1. Results obtained from the interpretation of the VES data showed three to six geoelectric layers.
2. The depth to top of the aquifer within the study area varies between 30m and 60m with location specific.
3. The aquifer thickness varies between 12.13m to 50m with an average thickness of 30m, which signifies an aquifer that is sufficient enough to produce a reasonable quantity of water over time.

4. It was observed that the hydraulic conductivity obtained ranges from 0.00684931 to 0.02024291cm/s while the transmissivity range is from 0.00476875 to 0.34050933cm²/s within the study area.

- **Recommendation**

This researched work can be used as a guide for further research studies by hydrological scientists for optimization of the environment and its natural resources (water). It is therefore recommended that for effective borehole siting within the study area, the targeted depth to top of the aquifer should be location specific within a range of 40m to 80m. This will ensure long term continuous supply of potable water for domestic, agricultural and industrial purposes within the study area and its environs.

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